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Regionalised factors for successful implementation of subsoil management: Evidence from three case studies in Germany

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Title Regionalised factors for successful implementation of subsoil management: Evidence from three case studies in Germany

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Abstract Farmers and other relevant stakeholders in Germany regard subsoil amelioration as an effective tool to improve the water storage of the subsoil and thereby to better bridge temporary water deficits. In addition, they acknowledge that subsoil amelioration can mitigate heavy rainfall events, as it improves infiltration and percolation of water in the soil. Building on this perception, this paper analyses relevant enabling and hindering factors for the implementation of subsoil management in a regional context, focusing on (i) geophysical conditions and (ii) relevant socio-economic criteria in selected regions of Germany. To this end, we mapped the potentials and needs for subsoil amelioration in three federal states in Germany and analysed regional farm statistics with a view on relevant socio-economic criteria. Based on these findings, the implications of mismatches between geophysical conditions and socio-economic criteria for the successful implementation of subsoil management in Germany are discussed. Furthermore, strategies are proposed to address the identified obstacles in agricultural management and policymaking.

Keywords subsoil, acceptance, Soil³, BonaRes

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Executive Summary

Farmers and other relevant stakeholders in Germany regard subsoil amelioration as an effective tool to improve the water storage of the subsoil and thereby to better bridge temporary water deficits. In addition, they acknowledge that subsoil amelioration can mitigate heavy rainfall events, as it improves infiltration and percolation of water in the soil. Building on this perception, this paper analyses relevant enabling and hindering factors for the implementation of subsoil management in a regional context, focusing on (i) geophysical conditions and (ii) relevant socio-economic criteria in selected regions of Germany. To this end, we mapped the potentials and needs for subsoil amelioration in three federal states in Germany and analysed regional farm statistics with a view on relevant socio-economic criteria. Based on the results, we discuss the potential implications of a mismatch of geophysical conditions and socio-economic criteria for the successful implementation of subsoil management in Germany and propose ways to address the identified obstacles in agricultural management and policymaking.

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1 Introduction

The risk of crop failures during hot and dry summers is on the increase both in Germany and worldwide due to climate change. Improved subsoil integration as a production factor in existing farm systems can be a means to tackle this challenge, as the subsoil holds large reserves of water, carbon and nutrients and could therefore help to stabilise and even increase yields. In response to this, the Soil³ project aims to contribute to sustainable subsoil management practices by developing and testing the following measures:

- i) improving subsoil properties through alfalfa cultivation and deep-rooting pre-crops (biological amelioration); and
- ii) deep loosening combined with the insertion of compost into deep soil layers (Soil³ technology) (mechanical amelioration).

In this paper, we analyse and discuss bio-drilling as an option for biological subsoil management. Bio-drilling involves the cultivation of plants with particularly deep and thick roots, which form continuous macropores (biopores) into the subsoil that can serve subsequent crops as “highways” into the subsoil (Kautz, 2014). For Germany, most research on bio-drilling has been done so far using alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) as a fodder crop (e.g., Gaiser et al., 2012; Kautz & Köpke, 2010). In contrast, mechanical techniques for subsoil amelioration include deep ploughing, deep loosening, and a novel approach of deep slotting (Soil³ technology) (Frelil-Larsen et al., 2018). This paper analyses and discusses the latter approach. This technique works with a new slotting device developed as part of the Soil³ project, which is used to insert organic material (e.g., compost) into the subsoil in stripes with minimal topsoil deterioration (Schmittmann et al., 2021).

The first German Agricultural Soil Inventory, covering all agricultural land across Germany on a regular 8 km x 8 km grid, revealed that 46% of agricultural land is compacted to such an extent that root growth is restricted, in addition to other inhibiting factors like anoxia, sandy texture, and acidity (Schneider et al., 2019). In the face of the challenges of global warming, it is crucial to address these root-restricting layers to enable deeper root growth and utilise water and nutrients from the subsoil (> 30 cm depth) when topsoil (0-30 cm depth) resources are depleted.

However, the effectiveness of subsoil amelioration strategies is soil- and region-specific and must be tailored to local site conditions to ensure success. Failure to adapt these methods can lead to reduced productivity, trafficability and workability of sites. Depending on the method, there are different exclusion criteria for subsoil amelioration. These criteria comprise conditions under which conducting the amelioration measure is either not possible at all or accompanied by a high risk of causing negative side effects.

The application of the Soil³ technology is not appropriate in shallow, non-diggable soils, i.e., the solid bedrock which starts within the upper 60 cm of soil. Similarly, shallow drainage pipes in the soil that could be damaged by the machinery used when applying this method are another exclusion criterion. The influence of groundwater can lead to anaerobic decomposition of organic material introduced by the Soil³ method, which could lead to significant emissions of nitrous oxide and other greenhouse gases (Weier et al., 1993). Consequently, shallow groundwater is also an exclusion criterion for the application of the Soil³ technology. The cultivation of alfalfa is subject to different restrictions: The rock and sand content, as well as soil acidity, must be assessed in advance, as exceeding certain thresholds will hinder or prevent the formation

and persistence of biopores. All of this must be checked before an appropriate method can be selected.

Apart from geophysical factors, previous research has demonstrated that the adoption of subsoil amelioration in Germany could be influenced by a variety of socio-economic factors. Hinzmann et al. (2021) identified a range of different socio-economic factors that determine the acceptance of subsoil amelioration among agricultural stakeholders in Germany, including economic and farm-level considerations, risk perception, environmental awareness, individual norms and beliefs and general awareness of subsoil's role in plant cultivation. These factors and their determinants vary across regions and farm types.

Given these considerations, it is important to identify the regions in Germany that are best suited for the implementation of subsoil amelioration measures. This involves not only identifying degraded soils from a geophysical perspective, but also considering the socio-economic environment that can support or hinder subsoil interventions. For instance, even if applying the Soil³ technology to compacted cropland could significantly increase crop yields, the improvement would still find little favour if the technical infrastructure and the required compost material were unavailable. The same applies to alfalfa cultivation (bio-drilling), which might meet little acceptance among farmers because they would need options for utilising and monetising the alfalfa biomass or would have to take their acreage out of the normal production cycle for at least one, or better two, growing seasons (Frelih-Larsen et al., 2018).

The aim of this paper is to determine which regions are suitable for subsoil amelioration, based on geophysical and socio-economic factors at the county level, within the federal states of North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW), Saxony-Anhalt (ST), and Brandenburg (BB). Additionally, we highlight and discuss mismatches between these factors and propose viable strategies to enhance both the adoption and effectiveness of subsoil management practices in German agriculture. By addressing these mismatches, this paper aims to provide novel insights that can lead to improved soil health and agricultural productivity across varied farming contexts in Germany.

2 Methods

2.1 Geophysical perspective

2.1.1 Exclusion criteria

To evaluate a site's overall potential for subsoil amelioration, a simplified binary scale was used to represent the exclusion criteria (1 = criterion applies; 0 = criterion does not apply). To facilitate this, threshold values were defined and are listed in Table 1. If an exclusion criterion applied to a site and an amelioration method, the site was categorised as unsuitable for amelioration. Although these threshold values were somewhat arbitrary and could affect results for individual sites, regional patterns remained stable despite minor adjustments to the thresholds (results not shown).

Table 1: Exclusion criteria for conducting bio-drilling (BD) and/or Soil³ technology (Soil³)

Property	Definition according to Schneider et al. (2020)	Affected technology
Shallow soil	Non-diggable, solid bedrock < 1 m depth	Soil ³ , BD
Rock fragments	20 vol-% rock fragments (> 2 mm)	BD

Sand	Main texture class: sand (according to AD-HOC-AG BODEN (2005))	BD
Acidity	pH _{H₂O} < 5	BD
Drainpipes	Subsoil with drainage pipes	Soil ³
Groundwater	Pedogenic horizon code “r”	Soil ³ , BD

Source: Schneider et al. (2020)

2.1.2 Digital soil mapping

Using the SCORPAN framework, thirty-two covariates representing soil (S factor), climate (C factor), organism (O factor), topography and relief (R factor), parent materials and lithology (P factor), and geographical position (N factor) were selected to train a model to spatially predict amelioration potential and need, bulk density, and clay content. This spatial prediction was done for five soil depth intervals (0–10 cm, 10–30 cm, 30–50 cm, 50–70 cm, 70–100 cm) using the 2.5D method. With this method, each depth is predicted independently, which reduces the prediction uncertainty (Ma et al., 2021). The depth intervals were chosen in accordance with the standard of the first German Agricultural Soil Inventory.

The spatial prediction was limited to mineral soil and cropland land use, excluding non-qualifying samples using the land use map (ATKIS Basis-DLM2019) and peatland maps (Roßkopf et al., 2015). From approximately 3100 samples in the inventory, 1917 were selected. Given the binary nature of the amelioration potential and need, the Random Forest (RF) algorithm for classification was chosen, while RF for regression was used for bulk density and clay content. The modelling involved tuning the ‘mtry’ hyperparameter of the RF and performance evaluation using K-fold spatial nested cross-validation. For spatial cross-validation, Germany was divided into 50 equal-sized strata, based on a 100 km by 100 km standardised INSPIRE grid. Random samples from each stratum were taken to create five folds, repeated three times. This approach ensured robust performance evaluation.

2.1.3 Classification system

After spatial prediction, maps were cross-checked to identify regions that were classified as demonstrating amelioration need and potential. These regions were overlaid with German county maps, and cropland pixels were counted to determine the percentage of soils requiring subsoil amelioration and the applicability of specific techniques (Soil³ technology or bio-drilling). Five classes were defined based on the percentage of overlap between need and applicability:

- Class 1 (0–20%): low need/applicability
- Class 2 (20–40%): moderate need/applicability
- Class 3 (40–60%): medium need/applicability
- Class 4 (60–80%): high need/applicability
- Class 5 (80–100%): very high need/applicability

2.2 Socio-economic perspective

2.2.1 Relevant criteria and weighting for the socio-economic maps

We have identified relevant socio-economic criteria for the implementation of mechanical and biological subsoil amelioration (Table 2). These are based on an acceptance analysis of 50 farmers and 36 soil experts (Hinzmann et al., 2021) and findings from Aghabeygi et al.

(forthcoming)¹, who identified and assessed key factors crucial for implementing diverse subsoil management practices. The key indicators were specified and weighted by their increasing relevance from factor (1) to (3) in terms of their potential to introduce the Soil³ technology and/or crops that support building biopores.

Table 2: Relevance of the socio-economic criteria

Socio-economic criterion	Weighting factor	Relevance
Relevance: deep-rooting pre-crops		
Farm type: mixed farming	3	The availability of opportunities to make further use of alfalfa has shown to be a significant factor in the acceptance of its cultivation (Hinzmman et al., 2021). These utilisation opportunities are closely related: For one, farmers with mixed farms can employ alfalfa or other deep-rooting crops as fodder for their livestock; for another, farms primarily engaged in crop cultivation may commercialise alfalfa by selling it to neighbouring livestock farmers. In addition, this provides a number of environmental benefits and fosters circular approaches and closed loops within agricultural systems. For instance, the utilisation of alfalfa as livestock feed not only provides nutrition, but also generates organic matter in the form of manure. This manure can then be recycled back into the soil as a natural fertiliser, promoting soil health and fertility for crop production.
Farm type: organic farming	2	The results of the acceptance analysis (Hinzmman et al., 2021) show that organic farms tend to be more willing to integrate deep-rooted plants such as alfalfa into their crop rotations. Since the use of mineral synthetic nitrogen fertilisers is not allowed in organic farming, the interest in methods that bind, increase or make available organic nitrogen for the plants is part of the farm philosophy. This suggests that the higher the proportion of organically farmed land in the region, the greater the potential for the bio-drilling method investigated in the Soil ³ project. It is assumed that it is easier to increase the proportion of deep-rooting plants in the crop rotation of a farm with an existing system of sustainable measures, than to perform a higher-threshold conversion to a highly specialised conventional farm.
Share of legumes	1	Regions with intensified legume cultivation besides alfalfa are more likely to provide a favourable environment for the adoption of alfalfa and other deep-rooting crops. This is due to several key factors such as existing knowledge and experience in the region, (potential) market demand, environmental considerations, and (potential) economic incentives. The cultivation of legumes suggests that farmers in these areas already recognise the benefits, such as

¹ Land ownership, which was indicated as an important factor for the implementation of the Soil³ technology in Aghabeygi et al. (forthcoming), was not included as a relevant criterion here, because the acceptance analysis showed that, despite some initial indications, it does not significantly impact the implementation of mechanical subsoil amelioration. While the group of the 'pioneers' and 'sceptics' agreed that land ownership is not a key factor for subsoil amelioration, the group of the 'ecologists' felt that the Soil³ technology would be more likely to be implemented on owned land. However, the effectiveness the Soil³ technology on leased land often depends on the lease duration: long-term leases are less problematic, whereas short-term leases may hinder implementation (see Hinzmman et al., 2021).

improved soil fertility, reduced need for nitrogen fertilisers, and diversified crop rotations. This understanding could lead to greater acceptance and openness to cultivate alfalfa. Differentiating between fodder and grain legumes could give a more accurate picture; however, in the available statistical data, both were grouped together.

Relevance: Soil³ technology

Share of specialised cultivation (vegetables)

1

As the cultivation of speciality crops (e.g. asparagus, onions, etc.) leads to higher revenues and farm incomes compared to other crops, there may be a greater willingness among farmers already dedicated to these crops to undertake additional, cost-intensive (approx. 750 Euros/ha) subsoiling. Regions with an above-average proportion of speciality crops can therefore be expected to have a higher potential for implementing the Soil³ technology. Thus, these regions are considered promising for the application of the Soil³ technology.

Regionally available compost

3

The implementation of the Soil³ technology requires substantial quantities of compost (40 m³/ha). The acceptance analysis carried out by Hinzman et al. (2021) concluded that the availability of substantial amounts of well-rotted, certified compost can significantly influence farmers' willingness to implement the Soil³ technology. In Germany, the distribution of composting facilities varies significantly among regions. For instance, in Eastern Germany, there is a lower density of these facilities, primarily due to the low production volume of compost. The likelihood of adopting the Soil³ technology is, however, not solely dependent on the presence of composting facilities, but also significantly influenced by the production capacities of these plants. Regions with high-capacity composting facilities are better equipped to meet the large demand for compost necessary for application of the Soil³ technology.

Relevance: deep-rooting pre-crops and Soil³ technology

Share of highly nitrate-polluted areas

3

The German nitrate regulation that follows the EU Nitrate Directive divides regions into three zones based on the level of water contamination: Green zones with low contamination levels, yellow zones with medium contamination levels, and red zones with high contamination levels. In regions designated as red or yellow areas², the Soil³ technology will most likely only be applied if it does not support the farmers' risk perception that it leads to higher nitrate pollution of groundwater or surface waters (Hinzmann et al., 2021). There is therefore a limited potential for implementing the Soil³ method in red and yellow areas. In regions where the proportion of measuring points with nitrate levels of 50 mg/l is the lowest or where a load of less than 50 mg/l was measured, the potential for implementing the Soil³ technology is the highest. On the other

² <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/themen/wasser/grundwasser/ueberwachung-bewertung/ausweisung-nitratbelasteter-gebiete>

side, in regions with high nitrate levels, the potential for biological subsoil amelioration is high due to nitrate fixation potentials.

Soil productivity

(Bodenpunkte)

3

It is assumed that if the soil's productivity (measured in so-called *Bodenpunkte*; soil points) is high, the need for better nutrient uptake and water supply is still not less relevant compared to low productive soils that often have low available water capacities for plants. Therefore, areas where lower soil qualities are given or are the result of continuous degradation over decades show huge potential for a need of an efficient use of nutrients. Mechanical and biological subsoil management could possibly help to improve the available soil nutrients for crops (Ning et al., 2022).

The maps showing the potential from a socio-economic perspective were developed using the geographic information system software QGIS. Most of the primary data was sourced from the Agricultural Structure Surveys for BB, NRW and ST, except for the map on the compost availability, for which data was sourced from Federal Compost Quality Association³.

2.3 Combining geophysical and socio-economic perspectives

In order to find out the overall implementation potential for subsoil amelioration, results from the evaluation of the geophysical and socio-economic factors were combined, and specific counties were selected for each of the methods, representing the following combinations:

- 1) The potential for implementing a subsoil amelioration method is high from a geophysical perspective, but low from a socio-economic perspective
- 2) The potential for implementing a subsoil amelioration method is low from a geophysical point of view, but high from a socio-economic perspective
- 3) The potential for implementing a subsoil amelioration method is high from a geophysical perspective and high from a socio-economic perspective
- 4) The potential for implementing a subsoil amelioration method is low from a geophysical perspective and low from a socio-economic perspective (not discussed here)

These combinations are discussed further in the results below. In the selected counties, we looked more closely at which individual key indicators have the greatest impact in the final assessment of this region. The socio-economic factors involved are as interdependent as the geophysical factors. A high score concerning one socio-economic factor does not necessarily lead to a high score concerning other factors nor the geophysical indicators. That is why each region deals with its own preconditions on many levels.

3 Results

3.1 Pressure for subsoil amelioration in the three case study regions

The regionalised maps were produced according to the methodology described in chapter 2.1.2 and are displayed in the supplemental material (Figs. A1–A3). From a geophysical perspective, the pressure for subsoil amelioration differed considerably among the three case study regions,

³ <https://www.kompost.de/service/hersteller/-produkte/karte-anlagen>.

with a generally low pressure (1) for subsoil amelioration in NRW, a medium pressure (3) for subsoil amelioration in ST, and a very high (5) pressure for subsoil amelioration in BB. This translates into the theoretical regional demand among farmers for subsoil amelioration measures to facilitate the use of subsoil resources. Due to the small-scale variability of soils and soil properties also in regions with low regional pressure, some field sites will have a high demand for subsoil amelioration and, vice versa, some field sites in regions with very high pressure have a low melioration demand.

Subsoil amelioration pressure weighting in Brandenburg, North Rhine-Westphalia and Saxony-Anhalt

Map 1: Visualisation of the score results for the pressure to perform subsoil amelioration per county in North Rhine-Westphalia, Saxony-Anhalt, and Brandenburg; 1 = very low, 2 = moderate, 3 = medium, 4 = high, 5 = very high.

3.2 Merged maps of the three case study regions displaying geophysical characteristics

The applicability of bio-drilling as an amelioration measure was low in BB, with every county scoring a value of one (Map 2). In ST, the applicability of bio-drilling was moderate, with a mean score of two across the federal state. Most counties in BB had lower scores. In NRW, the applicability of bio-drilling was also moderate, with a mean score of two across the federal state.

As shown in Map 3, the applicability of the Soil³ method in BB was very high, with every county scoring a value of five. Similarly, in ST, the applicability was also very high, with a mean score

of five across the federal state. In NRW, the applicability of the Soil³ method was high, with a mean score of four across the federal state.

3.3 Merged maps of the three case study regions displaying regionalised socio-economic characteristics

Maps 4 and 5 depict the applicability of bio-drilling and of the Soil³ technology in the three case study regions from a socio-economic perspective. For bio-drilling, the applicability is highest in BB, whereas NRW and ST show a medium applicability. The high potential in BB results from the underlying criteria: As the vast majority of the arable land there has soil productivity levels (*Bodenpunkte*) that are well below the German average, the room for improvement, i.e. the soil optimisation potential, is great. In addition, the low nutrient and water capacity leads to very little restriction given by the low number of farms in “red zones” (high levels of nitrate contamination) that are restricted by the Nitrate Directive. This is further supported by the high proportion of mixed farming businesses that are historically part of East German agriculture structures. This leads to a higher potential in the practical use of deep-rooting pre-crops like alfalfa as

animal feed for animal breeding, while acknowledging that, for the primarily use of alfalfa for cattle breeding, the numbers in BB are lower.

For the Soil³ technology, all three case study regions show a medium to very high applicability, although the results vary among the individual counties. This is because for the Soil³ technology, compost is placed into the subsoil and its regional availability is therefore a key factor in the method's implementation. This is affected by regional supply and production chains rather than landscape structures, leading to the counties themselves being heterogenous. The rather high general potential is again due to the combination of lower soil productivity and a small portion of areas that are highly polluted with nitrate and therefore potentially limited in the additional storage of nitrogen via organic material. The very low potential areas result from either city areas that lack farms in general or are fertile areas that have sufficient capacity as of now.

4 Discussion

The comparison of the three federal states shows that NRW faces less severe issues with root-restricting layers caused by compactness than ST and BB (Schneider et al., 2019). Drought stress increases from west to east, with exceptions in regions like the Main River and upper Rhine valley that are also drought susceptible (DWD, 2018). Consequently, compacted cropland in Eastern Germany, particularly in BB, has a higher need for subsoil amelioration in order to facilitate the access to additional plant available water in the subsoil (Map 1). The

varying degrees of compactness and drought stress across different regions of Germany highlight the need for targeted subsoil amelioration. However, as illustrated in the maps above, there is a notable mismatch between the geophysical and socio-economic factors influencing the implementation potential of subsoil measures in some of the regions. While certain areas may present geophysical constraints that hinder the application of mechanical or biological subsoil amelioration, the same regions might be considered highly suitable for such measures from a socio-economic perspective. This discrepancy arises because socio-economic factors, such as farm structure, availability of compost or farmers' experiences with the cultivation of legumes can significantly favour the adoption of subsoil amelioration practices despite the given geophysical limitations.

The analysis of both geophysical and socio-economic factors revealed that regions such as ST and BB exhibit a higher need for subsoil amelioration, but the choice of method depends on a balanced consideration of the constraints. For example, the southwestern regions of ST and NRW show medium to high socio-economic potential for amelioration practices, yet geophysical factors often limit the applicability of specific methods like bio-drilling or the Soil³ technology. The geophysical suitability may rule out large areas in BB and parts of ST, but socio-economic factors, such as the strong presence of organic farms or the availability of legumes, may still promote the use of bio-drilling in selected areas, even if the broader geophysical conditions seem less favourable.

It is important to note, however, that all values for pressure and applicability refer to average values in the counties. This does not necessarily imply that every cropland within a selected region inevitably requires subsoil amelioration, or that a particular method is generally suitable/unsuitable to all areas. Instead, the data shows that in some regions, the need for subsoil amelioration is greater or certain methods can be applied more easily.

4.1 Soil³ technology

For mechanical methods like the Soil³ technology, Eastern German areas with compacted soils derived from periglacial sand, such as BB and ST, are promising for the applicability of the technique due to their lower water balances and minimal pedological constraints (Schneider, 2020). This is consistent with the overall geophysical potential for the Soil³ technology in these regions, as the geophysical perspective shows a high application potential in both ST and BB. However, only the eastern and south-eastern parts of BB as well as the northern and central parts of ST show a higher suitability for the Soil³ technology from a socio-economic-point of view. The western part of ST, although geophysically suitable, has low socio-economic potential, which makes actual implementation more difficult. Regions with high geophysical but low socio-economic potential, such as the Börde county in ST, face challenges in adopting amelioration methods despite favourable soil conditions. This discrepancy can also be found in other parts of ST, where socio-economic factors such as farm structure and compost availability limit the feasibility of the Soil³ technology despite the overall promising geophysical conditions.

Despite the given differences, there are also noteworthy similarities from both a geophysical and socio-economic perspective. In regions such as Oberhavel (BB), both socio-economic and geophysical factors align, indicating high potential for successful mechanical subsoil amelioration. In addition, the areas on the border between BB and ST maintain a high potential for subsoil amelioration, since both the geophysical and socio-economic factors indicate a strong applicability for the Soil³ technology. Regions in NRW are less compacted and are in part dominated by more fertile soils and show a lower geophysical necessity for subsoil amelioration (Schneider et al., 2020). However, socio-economic factors, such as the availability of compost and cash crop farms might still encourage the adoption of amelioration practices. The potential for the Soil³ technology is particularly high in regions around Arnsberg and smaller parts in the

east and south of NRW. These areas were excluded due to geophysical constraints only in some northern counties such as Gütersloh, Warendorf, Coesfeld, Borken, and Steinfurt.

However, there are exceptions in NRW, where socio-economic challenges hinder the adoption of the Soil³ technology. For example, the absence of compost facilities in Düren is a significant drawback for the application of the Soil³ technology, as the availability of compost is crucial for its application. Additionally, 30% of the agricultural land there is affected by nitrate polluted groundwater, which is a relatively high percentage. This elevated nitrate level could influence farmers' risk perception and prevent them from applying the Soil³ technology due to concerns about nitrate leaching from soils to the groundwater. These factors make the county Düren less suitable for the implementation of the Soil³ technology.

Overall, the analysis shows that the Soil³ technology has broad potential in Eastern Germany, particularly in areas with compacted soils and low water balances. Still, socio-economic constraints in certain regions prevent an easy implementation. In NRW, while geophysical necessity is lower, socio-economic factors, such as compost availability and farm practices, play a more decisive role in determining where the method can be applied.

4.2 Bio-drilling

In general, regions in Eastern Germany, such as BB and ST, display a high prevalence of compacted cropland and increased drought stress, leading to a substantial need for subsoil amelioration (Schneider, 2020). From a geophysical perspective, these areas face challenges that hinder root access to subsoil resources, which is critical during drought periods. Consequently, regions like Teltow-Fläming, with high socio-economic potential but poor geophysical conditions for the implementation of bio-drilling, may struggle with the effectiveness of these subsoil interventions due to high sand content and shallow groundwater, which are both exclusion criteria for bio-drilling.

Despite these geophysical constraints, the socio-economic environment in many regions in Eastern Germany is suitable for implementing biological amelioration measures. From a socio-economic perspective, factors such as the availability of mixed farms, the number of organic farms as well as the proportion of legume cultivation make these regions suitable candidates for the cultivation of alfalfa. In BB, despite the unfavourable geophysical conditions that almost disqualify the bio-drilling method, socio-economic factors indicate a high potential for the cultivation of alfalfa.

According to Map 4, NRW is less suitable for bio-drilling from a socio-economic perspective. In the district of Düren, for example, well-aerated soils and a suitable pH range support the growth of tap-rooted plants like alfalfa. These favourable geophysical conditions, however, do not align with less favourable socio-economic conditions, making it a less suitable region for the bio-drilling method.

Regions with well-aerated loess soils, such as parts of Mansfeld-Südharz, show high potential for bio-drilling due to the favourable conditions for biopore stability. This area also meets all the socio-economic requirements, having a high proportion of mixed and organic farming in the region and a substantial need for a higher nitrate reservoir in the ground. These characteristics make regions like Mansfeld-Südharz key focus areas for subsoil amelioration through bio-drilling. Policymaking and incentives should be directed toward such regions to promote the more intensive adoption of bio-drilling techniques, particularly those using alfalfa cultivation.

In general, in comparison to other methods, bio-drilling presents fewer geophysical suitable areas. For instance, in BB and ST, where the pressure for subsoil amelioration is moderate to high, the overall geophysical applicability score for bio-drilling remains lower than in NRW,

where a few selected regions show better alignment between geophysical and socio-economic factors. However, as seen in regions like Soest, while there is potential for bio-drilling, the overall cropland needing amelioration is lower, reducing the immediate pressure for intervention.

5 Conclusions

The potential for successful implementation of subsoil amelioration measures depends on both geophysical and socio-economic factors. The optimisation of subsoil amelioration strategies requires an integrated approach that considers both the geophysical constraints on the use of subsoil resources and the socio-economic advantages. Regions with high potential in both aspects demonstrate the best preconditions for successful implementation, but other regions may still benefit from targeted interventions that address their specific local conditions. Our study provides a regional indication of the suitability of subsoil amelioration measures, but the numbers can only indicate the probability of successful implementation at the regional district level. Soil conditions and the agricultural infrastructure vary from farm to farm and may therefore differ from the regional average.

One of the key objectives of our analysis was to identify the regions in Germany that are best suited for subsoil amelioration, taking into account the different pressures, specific needs, and the prevailing socio-economic conditions across the three case study areas. Our analysis shows that the highest pressure for subsoil amelioration is observed in BB, followed by ST with a moderate pressure, and NRW with the lowest pressure. These variations can be attributed to the differences in the agrarian structure and the low level of available water and nutrients in the soil.

Moreover, our analysis has shown that geophysical and socio-economic factors are not invariably linked to each other, meaning that a high potential in one of these areas does not imply a high potential in the other. This can be seen in BB, where high socio-economic potential for deep-rooting crops meets a lower potential from a geophysical point of view, or in the region of Börde (NRW), where there is a high capability for the Soil³ technology from the geophysical perspective but a low socio-economic potential. This has implications for agricultural management and policymaking, as well as for scientific research.

Implications for farm management and agricultural policymaking

Based on these results, farmers, agricultural advisors and policymakers can assess whether a particular region is suitable for subsoil management and can then design regionally adapted policies to foster subsoil amelioration technologies with specific support programmes. Two key categories of factors influence this determination: geophysical and socio-economic factors. If there is a political determination to improve the management of subsoil conditions, these factors can be strategically addressed to strengthen the agricultural infrastructure, laying the foundation for successful subsoil amelioration. Geophysical preconditions, such as the influence of groundwater or depth of the solid bedrock, that hinder the implementation of a certain technology, cannot be changed. Therefore, the main focus in terms of agricultural policymaking should be on the relevant socio-economic factors, which provide possible intervention points for policymakers at federal state level (e.g. agricultural ministries) as well as at county level (e.g. boards of agriculture). For example, these factors include the availability of local compost or the number of organic farms. Although the most suitable regions for potential implementation are prioritised based on both perspectives, the question of how to address the mismatches remains, i.e. a) in regions where the geophysical characteristics are favourable for applications

of the Soil³ technology, but relevant socio-economic factors are hindering its application, and b) in regions with high potential for bio-drilling based on the region's geophysical characteristics, but where it is not considered socio-economically viable enough.

If there is an urgent need for subsoil amelioration in a specific region, an appropriate (politically intended) response in terms of subsoil management might not be practically feasible as the process is time-consuming. Therefore, policymakers and farm managers should act early and address questions such as "How can the situation be improved?" and "What are the relevant instruments to tackle unfavourable socio-economic factors?" The theoretical potential of the two subsoil amelioration techniques cannot be applied universally as our study has shown that the approach is based on a regional assessment using probabilities of different weighting factors. However, this is where opportunities arise for efficient water and nutrient use of the soil, a need that will certainly increase as climate conditions become more challenging.

The first step in deciding to support subsoil amelioration in a certain region is to determine the current status of subsoil management in the region. For instance, if a network supporting the use of bio-drilling already exists in the area, it can be expanded and strengthened to intensify the process. Otherwise, reaching out to farms in the region to find out their position on implementing bio-drilling or the Soil³ technology will be a key element. Barriers hindering the practical implementation of subsoil amelioration are identified best in close dialogue with farmers, farm advisors, farmers' associations, and technology providers. Such dialogues will be a crucial step in the successful practical implementation of subsoil amelioration. The ideal conditions for subsoil amelioration vary, however, from farm to farm and depend on all the different factors investigated in this paper.

Further concrete steps can be considered by policymakers at different levels. At the federal state level, agricultural ministries could offer financial support for the development of compost facilities, or they could subsidise programmes for intensified cultivation of alfalfa. Local boards of agriculture, on the other hand, could design and implement indirect measures such as using the structures of local associations, networks and schools for capacity building, awareness raising, trainings or information campaigns in suitable regions to support a better subsoil management.

In other regions, where a mismatch of the potentials complicates the introduction of the methods, it should be assessed to what extent, at which individual field sites and at what cost subsoil management is still an option despite unfavourable conditions at regional scale.

Implications for scientific research across disciplines

Our findings demonstrate the value of interdisciplinary research on topics of major scientific and social importance. Considering the geophysical or socio-economic results in isolation would have led to different conclusions regarding the theoretical feasibility of subsoil amelioration. This demonstrates that complex issues cannot be fully addressed by a single discipline. As agriculture is a complex system, agricultural research increasingly requires interdisciplinary efforts, bringing together not only the natural sciences and economics but also the humanities. However, there is still room for improvement in the agricultural sector when it comes to these interdisciplinary efforts that integrate natural sciences, economics as well as the humanities.

Additionally, our paper highlights the limitations of spatial resolution, which does not allow for site-specific decisions. It also acknowledges that not all relevant factors were considered in a real-life context. This gap suggests opportunities for further interdisciplinary research that explores these aspects more comprehensively and enhances the practical application of subsoil management strategies.

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Annex

Necessity of subsoil
amelioration

- no need
- need

Figure A1: Map of Germany showing the need for subsoil amelioration. Green areas show that there is no need for subsoil amelioration. Red areas show that there is a need of subsoil amelioration.

Applicability of bio-drilling method

- not applicable
- applicable

Figure A2: Map of Germany showing the suitability to apply the bio-drilling method with increasing the number of bio-pores in the subsoil (BP). Green areas show that it is easily possible to implement the method due to exclusion criteria explained in the main document. Red areas show that it is difficult to implement the method.

Applicability of Soil3
technology

- not applicable
- applicable

Figure A3: Map of Germany showing the suitability to implement the Soil³ technology that loosens the subsoil and incorporates compost afterwards. Green areas show that it is easily possible to implement the method due to exclusion criteria explained in the main document. Red areas show that it is difficult to implement the method.

agricultural mixed-farms 2020 in
Brandenburg, North Rhine-Westphalia and Saxony Anhalt

Figure A4: Map of the three case study regions NRW, ST and BB showing the individual weighting factors, here: share of arable land on a district level.

organic agricultural land 2020 in
Brandenburg, North Rhine-Westphalia and Saxony Anhalt

Legend:
organic
agricultural land

Editor: Ecologic Institut
Data source: Statistische Ämter des
Bundes und der Länder, DE (2023)
Projection: Transverse Mercator

Figure A5: Map of the three case study regions NRW, ST and BB showing the individual weighting factors, here: share of arable land used by organic farms on a district level

soil productivity (Bodenpunkte) map 2020 in
Brandenburg, North Rhine-Westphalia and Saxony Anhalt

Legend:
average soil
productivity

Editor: Ecologic Institut
Data source: Gutachterausschuss
für Grundstückswerte Sachsen-Anhalt (2021);
LELF (2022); Geologischer Dienst NRW (2023)
Projection: Transverse Mercator

Figure A6: Map of the three case study regions NRW, ST and BB showing the individual weighting factors, here: average level of soil productivity (Bodenpunkte) on a district level

cultivation area of legumes 2020 in
 Brandenburg, North Rhine-Westphalia and Saxony Anhalt

Legend:
 cultivation area
 of legumes

- No data available
- 0% to less than 1.5%
- 1.5% to less than 3%
- 3% to less than 4.5%
- 4.5% to less than 6%
- 6% to less than 8%

Editor: Ecologic Institut
Data source: Amt für Statistik
 Berlin-Brandenburg (2021);
 Landwirtschaftskammer NRW (2020);
 Statistisches Landesamt Sachsen-Anhalt (2022)
Projection: Transverse Mercator

N

 0 30 60 120 180 240 Kilometer

Figure A7: Map of the three case study regions NRW, ST and BB showing the individual weighting factors, here: share of legumes on a district level

cultivation area of special crops 2020 in
Brandenburg, North Rhine-Westphalia and Saxony Anhalt

Figure A8: Map of the three case study regions NRW, ST and BB showing the individual weighting factors, here: share of horticulture on a district level

nitrate load map 2020 in
Brandenburg, North Rhine-Westphalia and Saxony Anhalt

Legend:
agricultural
land with more
than 50 mg/l
nitrate

Editor: Ecologic Institut
Data source: VSR-Gewässerschutz e.V. (2023)
Projection: Transverse Mercator

0 30 60 120 180 240 Kilometer

Figure A9: Map of the three case study regions NRW, ST and BB showing the individual weighting factors, here: share of arable land with more than 50 mg/l average nitrate on a district level

Figure A10: Map of Germany displaying the clustered regional distribution of compost facilities. Source: <https://www.kompost.de/service/hersteller/-/produkte/karte-anlagen>, accessed on 5 March 2024

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